

IMPACT DAMAGE IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Damage resistance of composite laminates is being investigated with the objective of developing a correlation between the impact energy, and the size and distribution of damage within the material. A series of impact tests of T800H/3900-2 carbon/epoxy composite specimens were done at different energy levels. Dynamic force and strains were measured and, following the impact, the damage state in the specimens was determined using non-destructive and destructive examination methods. The impact event was modelled using finite element code DYNA3D, and predictions of the strain histories were made. Comparisons between the predicted and measured strains show reasonable agreement. This work is the initial stage of a project to develop a prediction method for behaviour of composite laminates after impact.

Keywords: Composite Materials, Graphite/Epoxy, Toughened Resins, Impact, Damage Resistance.

1. INTRODUCTION

Impact loading of composite laminates causes internal damage which can significantly reduce the residual strength of these materials, particularly in compression. Reduction of strength is of concern particularly when the impact is at low velocity and energy because the resulting damage is difficult to detect. This behaviour is one of the major limitations on the use of composites in aerospace structures, and has been the subject of a number of research projects. Two distinct aspects of the impact behaviour have been identified [1]. The impact **damage resistance** of a material relates to the size and distribution of damage caused by an impact (at a certain energy level). The **damage tolerance** is a property of a material to maintain its residual compressive strength in the presence of damage. Research work to-date has resulted in several semi-empirical methods which enable an estimate of the residual strength from the extent of damage, for example [2].

Damage resistance studies described in this paper represent the initial phase of a research program being undertaken jointly by the Structures and Materials Laboratory (SML) and Carleton University to gain an understanding of the impact behaviour of advanced composites and to develop methods to predict impact damage resistance and tolerance levels. Work on damage tolerance is described elsewhere [3].

The experimental part of this project was started by fabricating and then impacting a number of test specimens under controlled conditions. In parallel, the impact event was simulated using DYNA3D finite element code. The objective of this initial modelling was to predict the response in terms of strains at a point on the specimen surface, and to compare the calculated results to those measured during experiments. Comparisons were done for low energy impact levels assuming no failure, and for higher energy levels with and without failure modelling. Work is continuing in building confidence with the code and will proceed further in modelling initiation and growth of damage during impact, the ultimate aim of this task.

2. EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

2.1 Material and Test Specimens

The material system selected for this investigation was Toray T800H/3900-2, Grade 190, Type 35, an example of the latest generation of toughened resin-based systems. Test specimens were made in six different layups; however, only a "baseline" layup $[-45/0/+45/90]_3$ will be considered in this report. Material plies were precut from a roll of prepreg and, using alignment templates, were laid up by hand to form large panels. The panels were vacuum bagged and cured in an autoclave in accordance with the manufacturer's recommendations. Following the cure and inspections for internal defects, test specimens were cut from the panels to the requirements of the Boeing Specification BSS 7260 [4]. Final specimen dimensions of 102 mm (4 in) by 152 mm (6 in) were achieved by grinding. Average specimen thickness was measured to be 4.54 mm, corresponding to a ply thickness of 0.19 mm. Conformance with the specifications in [4] was determined by a set of dimensional inspections.

2.2 Test Equipment

A Dynatup Model 8200 instrumented drop weight system with a GRC 730-I instrumentation package was used for impact testing. In this system, an impactor containing a load cell is dropped from a fixed distance above the specimen. The load cell measures the load during the impact and 1024 data points are recorded over a time interval of 10 ms. Velocity just prior to impact is measured by an infrared system which also starts the load data acquisition. A latching device prevents repeated impacts. The test specimen is impacted at its centre and is supported by an anvil which is perpendicular to the line of action of the impactor. The anvil assembly was made to the requirements of BSS 7260 Class 1 Impact, and the arrangement can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Boeing Class 1 Impact Fixture

Strain data was gathered by mounting a biaxial strain gauge (2 mm gauge length) on the upper ply of the specimen approximately 36 mm from the specimen centre. One gauge element was aligned with the ply fibre direction, and the other perpendicular to the fibre. Strain signals were measured and amplified using Pacific Instruments transducer amplifiers Model 8255, and were captured in a two-channel Nicolet storage oscilloscope Model 3091. Data was downloaded to a PC for analysis.

2.3 Testing and Experimental Results

Initial tests were done at an energy level of 5.6 J (1.43 m/s), which was expected to cause little damage. These tests served to check out the test system and to provide load and strain data suitable for assessment of performance of the numerical predictions of the specimen response in the absence of failure. In the specimens tested at this energy level, the strain gauges were aligned with the global specimen co-ordinates (x-lengthwise) rather than with the upper ply orientation as described above.

Test specimens for the main program were impacted at the following five nominal energy levels

Energy [J]	15.5	30.8	40.9	51.7	61.8
Velocity [m/s]	2.39	3.37	3.88	4.36	4.77

according to Boeing Specification BMS 8-276 [5]. Five specimens were impacted at each energy level, followed by extensive inspections using ultrasonic (transmission and time-of-flight) and X-ray methods. Selected specimens were cut, polished and fractographically examined to confirm the non-destructive test results. The remaining specimens were subjected to compression-after-impact tests. Procedures and results of the damage assessment and the compression tests are detailed in reference [6].

Figure 2 Impact Load History

The impact load-time traces were repeatable from specimen to specimen at each energy level suggesting that the type and extent of damage due to impact should be similar. Non-destructive examinations confirmed this result. Load-time traces from all energy levels are shown superimposed in Figure 2 and several aspects of the impact behaviour of this composite material

and layup can be seen. The load initially increases almost linearly with time but with small-scale reversals. Energy associated with this portion of impact is largely elastic although some delaminations do take place as determined from tests at 5.6 J. An abrupt change in the nature of the load can be seen at approximately 11 kN where a series of large oscillations occur indicating that damage in the specimen is growing. Energy associated with this phase is irrecoverable. With an increase of the impact energy level, the duration of the inelastic energy absorption also increases. The dynamic load of 11 kN can be thought of as corresponding to an energy "threshold", found to be approximately 29 J. Below the threshold, damage consists primarily of delaminations. Above this value, significant matrix cracking and fibre failures take place. The threshold load was not reached in tests at 5.6 and 15.5 J, and inspections of the impacted specimens confirmed that the damage consisted mainly of delaminations.

Figure 3 Dynamic Strains - 5.6 J Impact Energy

The dynamic strain data was not acquired during all of the tests due to problems with instrumentation. At the low energy level of 5.6 J, three repeated impacts were applied to one specimen. Figure 3 shows that measured strain response was virtually identical, meaning that any damage formed during the first impact was local and did not grow significantly during the subsequent tests. The damaged area was measured by ultrasonic C-scan and can be approximated by a circle with diameter of 7.5 mm. In comparison, the local dent made by the impactor has a diameter of approximately 4.3 mm.

Strain signals were repeatable for tests at the same energy levels, similar to load data. X-strains (in the fibre direction) show particularly good repeatability. With increasing energy levels, the peak strain magnitudes also increased up to a maximum of approximately 6000 $\mu\text{m}/\text{m}$. This value was reached for the energy levels above 30.8 J. Y-strain (transverse to fibre) data is much more scattered but a maximum of approximately 2500 $\mu\text{m}/\text{m}$ can be discerned and the behaviour is the same as the x-strain. Duration at the maximum level increases with the impact energy. The strain traces are similar to the load traces when considering the impact duration and the presence of reversals. A typical strain history is shown in Figure 4 for the impact energy of 40.9 J.

Figure 4 Dynamic Strains - 40.9 J Impact Energy

3. NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION

3.1 Model

A numerical simulation of the Dynatup experiment was undertaken to examine the response of the composite specimen during the impact. These calculations were used to examine the nature of the stress wave propagation and the strains within the specimen. The analysis was performed using the DYNA3D finite element code [7].

Figure 5 Exploded view of FEM Model

Figure 5 shows the finite element mesh used to model the experiment. The test specimen was modelled using shell elements based on the formulation of Belytschko and Tsay [8]. Through-thickness integration of the shells employed a 24-point trapezoid rule. Each integration station corresponded to an individual ply to which were assigned the following in-plane orthotropic elastic properties:

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{11} &= 152.4 \text{ GPa} & E_{22} &= 9.205 \text{ GPa} \\
 E_{12} &= 4.275 \text{ GPa} & \nu_{12} &= 0.35
 \end{aligned}$$

Failure of the material was based on the Tsai-Wu model using the following ply properties:

$$X_T=2089.0 \text{ MPa} \quad X_C=1482.0 \text{ MPa}$$

$$Y_T=79.29 \text{ MPa} \quad Y_C=231.0 \text{ MPa} \quad S=132.8 \text{ MPa}$$

X and Y refer to the longitudinal and transverse values of strength and S is the in-plane shear strength.

The impactor assembly (tup) and anvil have stiffnesses well in excess of the test specimen bending stiffness. These components were treated as rigid bodies and only the surface regions of the impactor and anvil that were directly in contact with the specimen were discretized as seen in Figure 5. The anvil was fully constrained kinematically and the impactor was only allowed to move in the vertical direction. The element size within the specimen was 2.12 x 2.12 mm which was considered to be rather large. Future work will consider a more refined mesh.

The impactor assembly mass was 5.44 kg, equal to the sum of the individual masses of the impactor, load cell and extra weights. Calculations were run in which initial velocities corresponding to those in the experiments were assigned to the tup.

An intermittent contact algorithm was used to model the impact of the tup on the plate and the bearing forces of the plate on the anvil. This algorithm checks for penetration of the nodes on one surface through the element faces of the mating surface. If penetration is detected, a penalty function, equivalent to a "spring stiffness" between the surfaces, is added to the system of equations to correct or eliminate the penetration. Once the two surfaces separate, the penalty function is removed until contact or penetration reoccurs. This approach is well suited for generalized contact problems and conserves energy across the interface.

3.2 Results from Numerical Simulation

The predicted strain responses for impact energies of 5.6 J and 40.9 J are plotted in Figures 3 and 4, respectively (symbols). The values plotted are the surface strains from the element(s) nearest the strain gauge location. In Figure 3 it is observed that, while the magnitudes of the predicted strains are similar to the measured values, the predicted duration of loading is too short. This result demonstrates that the model response is too stiff and is probably due to insufficient mesh refinement and to the treatment of the tup-specimen interface. The use of a rigid, lumped-mass impactor neglects the flexibility of the impactor assembly. In addition, the flexibility associated with indentation of the plate by the tup is neglected since the model is based upon a shell formulation, and through-thickness deformation caused by the Hertzian contact is not considered. It is felt that mesh refinement and incorporation of these additional flexibilities into the model would increase the predicted period.

The effect of failure on the predicted specimen response is seen in Figure 4. Calculations in which the Tsai-Wu failure criterion was disabled have also been plotted and show higher strains at the strain gauge and a shorter period. The effect of failure near the tup is to reduce the loads transmitted to regions of the plate away from the tup. Thus the predicted strains decrease and the period increases to absorb the kinetic energy of the tup. As seen in the figure, the predicted period was less than that measured. The magnitude of the strains, predicted using the Tsai-Wu failure criterion, compares favourably with the data. The increase in strain and load duration with impact energy is also captured qualitatively well by the model as seen by comparing Figures 3 and 4.

The predicted strain histories for the 5.6 J impact from calculations in which the failure criterion had been disabled were identical to the predicted values in Figure 3 which considered damage. Thus, the numerical model did not predict damage to occur at this impact energy which was consistent with observations of the specimens after the test.

CONTOUR	STRAIN
A	0.0
B	0.002
C	0.006
D	0.010
E	0.020
F	0.080

Figure 6 Lower Surface Strains at 1 ms

Figure 7 Lower Surface Strains at 2 ms

Figures 6 and 7 show the predicted contours of in-plane maximum principal strain on the lower surface of the 40.9 J test at 1 ms and 2 ms after impact, respectively. At 1 ms, failure has only just initiated and the predicted contours are nearly symmetric with respect to the specimen. At 2 ms, it can be observed that a band of strain localization has occurred roughly along the specimen diagonal. This localization (failure) is oriented along the surface ply direction, as was observed experimentally, and is triggered by failure of this ply.

4. DISCUSSION

The experimental work has provided detailed information about the behaviour of Toray T800H/3900-2 material under impact. Dynamic force and strains have been measured, and the extent of damage has been characterized. This information is being used to develop and assess a finite element-based simulation of the impact.

The initial finite element predictions captured the magnitude of the strains and the increase in strain with impact energy relatively well. Some concerns exist over the excessive stiffness of the numerical model. In future work, additional flexibility terms will be introduced between the tup and plate to determine the effect of indentation on the predicted period of loading. The post-failure response will also be examined in detail to attempt to model the progressive failure or delamination of plies during impact. The resulting damage predictions will be compared to the results of non-destructive examinations, for all the material layups.

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